

Aweikoma

also known as “Xokleng”, “Kaingáng”, “Caingang”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

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** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: South American Religions, Religious Group

The Aweikoma traditionally inhabited a large area in what is now the state of Santa Catarina, Brazil, and lived in small, exogamous patrilineal clans. These highly mobile bands were led by chiefs, whose authority was limited. In 1914 the Aweikoma were pacified by the Brazilian Government and relocated to Duque de Caxias Reservation (near Ibirama). This entry focuses on the Aweikoma living on the reservation around the time of 1932, when the principal ethnographic authority, anthropologist Jules Henry, began a two-year ethnographic study in the area. This entry primarily relies on Henry's field work, which broadly covers Aweikoma life but provides somewhat limited information on the religious realm of life. Traditional Aweikoma religious beliefs and practices were able to be documented as the Brazilian government resisted attempts to establish missions (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941: xvi). These beliefs involve a variety of supernatural beings, including the spirits of deceased humans (referred to as ghost-souls or *kuplêng*), and monsters (Kuchágn Yunggi Wangdjó Yóin and Véin). The monsters, ghost-soul, and spirits of the natural world are collectively called *nggÿúdn*. According to Henry, shamans served as religious practitioners in former times, but no shamans were still living during the time of his visit. For the Aweikoma, religion does not exist within its own distinct sphere of life, but rather, is bound up with the functioning of society as a whole. Consequently, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with Aweikoma society as a whole.

Date Range: 1909 CE - 1934 CE

Region: Duque de Caxias Reservation, state of Santa Catarina, Brazil ca. 1932

Region tags: South America, Brazil

Duque de Caxias Reservation, state of Santa Catarina, Brazil ca. 1932

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: *Cross-Cultural Codes 3. Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 3: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: *Cross-cultural codes 4. Ethnology*,

11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sm03-002>

– Source 1 Description: Henry, Jules, Ruth Benedict, and Hans F. Kraus. 1941. "Jungle People: A Kaingang Tribe Of The Highlands Of Brazil." Locust Valley, New York: J. J. Augustin.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "Since that time [of pacification, around 1914] the government [of Brazil] has steadily resisted all attempts to establish missions among them. Although there is a Catholic church about five miles away from the reservation its effect on the Kaingáng has been practically nil" (Henry, Benedict, & Kraus, 1941:xvi).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (resolved rating), originally coded "0" for the Aweikoma, indicating that no resolved rating was made. Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (resolved rating), indicates that external warfare seems to be absent or rare. Additionally, SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, was indicated to have ambiguous or contradictory information. Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that the Aweikoma would actively recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Aweikoma religion does not exist within its own separate sphere of life, religion is bound up with the functioning of society at large. Therefore, the religious group is considered to be coterminous with Aweikoma society itself; consequently, this entry considers the religion to have political support.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 106

Notes: "Since 1914 when the Kaingáng were pacified and localized at Duque de Caxias epidemics have reduced their number from between three and four hundred to 106, and a number of changes have come over their culture" (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:xv).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The principal ethnographic authority, Jules Henry (who visited the Aweikoma from 1932-1934), indicated that "there are no Kaingáng shamans today; the few there were have died" (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:74).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: After death, the spirit of the deceased travels to the afterlife, which indicates that a spirit-body distinction is present (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:95).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "As far back as they can remember, the Kaingáng have been a dying people. Hunted by foreign enemies and torn by conflict from within, they lived in the shadow of death, sleeping fitfully beside their campfires, awakening to peer with frightened eyes into the solid darkness around them. Nor did their imaginations conceive a happier life: their afterworld is a somber reproduction of this one. There the people still hunt vendetta enemies, there the honey tastes like water, and there there is no meat to eat but the grubs in rotten wood" (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:95).

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– I don't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of a belief in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the bodies of the deceased are buried (see questions below), but burials and funeral customs are not described in substantial detail.

Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "It really does the Kaingáng no good to flee from the ghost-soul, for although it has a tendency to lurk about the place where the bones of its dead body are buried, it also is nomadic like the Kaingáng and may dog their footsteps wherever they go" (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:66).

Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: "When a child under twelve dies, it is placed in a grave in a sitting position..." (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:85).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1850, secondary bone/body treatment: original scale, indicates that, "secondary contact with the body or bones is the preferred means of disposal for all or nearly all adult members of the society" (Schroeder, 2011; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence.

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the spirits of deceased humans, several supernatural monsters are present among the Aweikoma, including Kuchágn Yunggí Wangdjó Yóin and Véin (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:70-71)

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 238, High Gods [note, equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34: high gods], indicates that a high god is absent or not reported (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Previously human spirits are present, but not described in substantial ethnographic detail. "The ghost-soul is called *kuplêng*, but together with the monsters and the spirits of the natural world, it is also called *nggÿúdn*" (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:71).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: "The ghost-soul loves and pities the living whom it has deserted, but the latter fear and abhor the ghost-soul. The ghost-soul longs for those it has left behind, but they remain cold to its longing" (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:67).

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Several supernatural monsters are present among the Aweikoma, including Kuchágn Yunggi Wangdjó Yóin and Véin (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:70-71). "The ghost-soul is called kuplêng, but together with the monsters and the spirits of the natural world, it is also called nggÿúdn. The spirits of the natural world dwell everywhere—in trees, under the water, in rocks, and in cliffs. They inhabit the sun and the moon and the stars, and animate the wind and the storm. There are the spirits of the tapir, the deer, the squirrel, the snake, and all other animals and insects" (ibid, pg. 71).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "These spirits [of the natural world] may appear to humans in their natural form or in the shape of human beings" (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:71).

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural monsters are generally malevolent, causing harm to humans (see Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:70-71).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the spirits of deceased humans, several supernatural monsters are present among the Aweikoma, including Kuchágn Yunggi Wangdjó Yóin and Véin (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:70-71).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of supernatural monitoring. However, supernatural beings are not described in enough detail to make a confident conclusion.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: "The society is politically semi-autonomous, being governed by another society with an alien culture which operates largely through the indigenous political institutions, e.g., through indirect rule, but which requires conformity on major issues such as refraining from war, head-hunting, or cannibalism" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 1: Political Autonomy). Note that this case was indicated to have a rating which is doubtful or based on inference. "There were no territorial boundaries to limit the range of the hunter, there was no chief or government to impose its will on the people" (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:49). "The Kaingáng inhabit an enormous territory. Through this land they scatter in small groups in search of food, for there is not enough game concentrated in any one area to support a large population. The small hunting bands are made up of men who are related as brothers, as fathers and children, and as in-laws. This is the standard composition of the bands from the Kaingáng point of view" (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:97).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of formal education among the Aweikoma.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "Police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 10: police).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: "Supreme judicial authority is lacking at any level above that of the local community" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 9: Judiciary).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: "Although the Kaingáng are now small farmers they still spend about half their time hunting" (Henry, Benedict, and Kraus, 1941:xvi).